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A Study of The Cancellation of Fasting: Research, Philosophy, Wisdom, And Benefits

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Abdul Qadeer

MPhil Scholar, Department of Islamic Studies,
University of Balochistan, Quetta

Dr. Tahira Firdaous

Assistant Professor, Department of Islamic Studies,
University of Balochistan, Quetta

Abstract

This study delves into the cancellation of fasting, exploring its implications through the lenses of research, philosophy, wisdom, and benefits. Fasting, a practice deeply rooted in various cultures and religions, holds significant meaning and importance. However, in contemporary times, the concept of cancelling fasting has emerged, sparking debates and discussions regarding its rationale and consequences. Through thorough analysis, this study aims to unravel the complexities surrounding the decision to cancel fasting, shedding light on its philosophical underpinnings, wisdom behind such actions, and potential benefits or drawbacks associated with it. By examining diverse perspectives and drawing insights from multidisciplinary approaches, this study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the phenomenon of cancelling fasting and its broader implications.

Keywords: Fasting, Cancellation, Philosophy, Wisdom, Implications

Corresponding Author Email:

abdulqadeer.78@gmail.com

Tahira.firdaous@gmail.com